

Effect of Autoclave Sterilization on the Cyclic Fatigue Resistance of Dentsply Protaper Next, Mani Jizai, and Twisted Nickel Titanium Endodontic Rotary Files: An In Vitro Study

Priya Hora¹, Aruna Kanaparth², Anurag Jain³, Sonal Bansal⁴, Srishti Chaturvedi⁵, Mansi Singh⁶

Received on: 28 - 05 - 2025; Accepted on: 04 - 06 - 2025; Published on : 22 08 2025

Post Graduate Student¹
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Professor and Head²
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Professor³
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Reader⁴
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Post Graduate Student⁵
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Post Graduate Student⁶
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Maharana Pratap College of Dentistry and Research Centre
Gwalior, (M.P)

Abstract

Introduction: Using nickel titanium (NiTi) rotational endodontic files increased the predictability of chemomechanical cleaning and shaping; however, instrument separation is a possibility and has been mentioned as a complication in the endodontic literature. Cyclic fatigue occurs as a result of repeated bending of the instruments in curved canals that lead to deformation and stress within the instruments, which end up with fracture due to complete tension compression cycles. Sterilization of NiTi files must be ensured before clinical use, with the exception of those that are presterilized. In this study we are comparing the cyclic fatigue resistance of Dentsply Protaper Next rotary files, Mani Jizai NiTi rotary files, and Sybron Endo Twisted rotary files, in a single curved simulated canal before and after autoclave sterilization.

Aim: This study aims to measure and compare the cyclic fatigue resistance of Dentsply Protaper Next rotary files, Mani Jizai rotary files, and Sybron Endo Twisted rotary files in a simulated canal before and after autoclave sterilization.

Materials and Method: 66 NiTi rotary files of the same size, i.e., having a tip diameter of 0.25 mm and constant taper 0.06 were used in this study. The files were distributed into 3 groups, each group having 22 files. Then each group was subdivided into two, sterilized and non-sterilized, subgroups having 11 files each. The files were selected on the basis of their metallurgical properties. The files were distributed as Group A: Dentsply Protaper Next; Group B: Mani Jizai; and Group C: Sybron Endo Twisted rotary files. The files were tested using a stainless steel plate. The number of cycles to fracture was calculated.

Results: It was observed that increased resistance to cyclic fatigue was seen among non-sterilized files as compared to the sterilized files. Mani Jizai files showed significantly higher fracture resistance than the other files used i.e. Dentsply Protaper Next and Sybron Endo Twisted files.

Conclusion: The study provides valuable insights into the selection of NiTi files, their metallurgical properties, and importance of sterilization. As the effect of clinical use was not evaluated in this study, further clinical investigations should be performed.

Introduction

The use of nickel titanium (NiTi) rotary endodontic files improved the predictability of mechanical cleaning and shaping; in spite of this, instrument separation is a possibility and has been mentioned as a complication in the endodontic literature.¹

These instruments offer remarkable advancements, such as improved flexibility, increased resistance to torsional stress, and an overall enhancement in performance.²

Despite the exceptional properties of NiTi instruments, they still can be separated due to cyclic or flexural fatigue. Cyclic fatigue occurs due to repeated bending of the

instruments in curved canals that lead to deformation and stress within the instruments, which ultimately results in fracture due to complete tension compression cycles.³

Many factors influence cyclic fatigue: the curvature of the canal, instrument dimensions, their design, and manufacturing process.⁴

The distinctive characteristics of NiTi alloy such as super elasticity and shape memory are greatly influenced by the

Access this article online

Website : www.healtalk.in

Quick Response Code

How to cite this article :

manufacturing procedure of the file.⁵

When files are used repeatedly under clinical conditions, it requires autoclave sterilization after every use. Prearranged collections of chosen files are not permitted for use during the same appointment. Consequently, the unused rotary files are also subjected to multiple autoclave cycles.⁶

Numerous advancements in contemporary manufacturing methods, such as thermal and surface treatments, have been achieved. A particularly innovative NiTi alloy known as M-wire, which was introduced in 2007 by Dentsply, Tulsa, Oklahoma, USA, was created utilizing these advanced manufacturing techniques. Its enhancement in flexibility and cyclic fatigue resistance is due to the unique nanocrystalline martensitic microstructure of the treated alloy.⁷ Dentsply protaper next rotary files comes under M-wire technology.

Twisted File (TF) represents a category of NiTi rotary files created by Sybron Endo (Orange, California). Introduced in 2008, this file was produced using an innovative manufacturing process that incorporates three novel techniques: heat treatment (R-phase), the twisting of the metal wire, and specialized surface conditioning.⁸

NiTi rotary instruments made from a NiTi controlled memory wire or CM wire (DS Dental, Johnson City, TN) was introduced.⁹ It was introduced in 2010. A novel file system named Jizai (Mani Inc., Tochigi, Japan) has been introduced, offering attributes such as enhanced strength and flexibility that minimizes canal transportation. It is designed to instrument straight and slightly curved canals.¹⁰

In this study we are comparing the cyclic fatigue resistance of Dentsply Protaper Next rotary files, Mani Jizai NiTi rotary files, and Sybron Endo Twisted rotary files, in a single curved simulated canal before and after autoclave sterilization.

Materials and Method

66 nickel titanium rotary files of the same size having tip diameter 0.25 mm and constant taper of 0.06 were used in this study. The files were distributed into 3 groups (22 for each group), Group A: Dentsply Protaper Next; Group B: Mani Jizai; and Group C: Sybron Endo Twisted rotary files. Then each group was subdivided into 2, sterilized and non sterilized, subgroups (11 for each group). For the sterilized instruments, three cycles of sterilization was used. Autoclave (GDP Enclave B-Class, Dibya Industries, India) was used for the sterilization. Each cycle lasted 35 minutes at a temperature of 134°C. A specially designed artificial canal was used for testing cyclic fatigue. It had an angle of curvature of 60° with a radius of 5 mm. It had a curvature center at 5 mm from the canal end, and the length of the curve of 5.25 mm. A stainless steel plate was utilized to shape the artificial canal. It had a working length of 18 mm and an inner diameter of 1.5 mm. A stereomicroscope was used to examine the instruments for any signs of deformation that would lead to their exclusion. The speed and torque of the endomotor (Dentsply X-SMART) was used following the manufacturer's instructions. In order to keep the endomotor in its position, it was secured to a surveyor

during the procedure. The files were rotated until separation was observed. A fracture was discovered, and the time taken from the beginning of file rotation to the point of separation was noted in minutes. By multiplying the recorded duration by the motor's speed, we could determine the cycle count at which each instrument ultimately fractured. The length of each broken fragment from the files was assessed using a vernier caliper.

Fig: Stainless Steel Plate with Artificial Canal

Fig: Endomotor secured to a Surveyor during Procedure

Results

Increased resistance to cyclic fatigue was seen among non-sterilized files as compared to the sterilized files. Mani Jizai files showed significantly higher fracture resistance than the other files, i.e. Dentsply Protaper Next and Sybron Endo Twisted files.

Discussion

The introduction of rotary instruments composed of nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) alloy was a turning point in modern endodontics.¹¹ Buehler created the nickel-titanium (NiTi) intermetallic alloy at the beginning of the 1960s. Nitinol, an abbreviation referring to its composition (Ni stands for nickel, Ti for titanium, and Nol for the Naval Ordinance Laboratory where it was invented), is another name for the NiTi alloy. In 1988, Walia produced size 15 hand files using nitinol orthodontic wire, publishing the first study on the flexibility, resistance, and cutting capacity of new files in NiTi in the field of endodontics. The endodontic market thereafter saw the commercial proposal of various instrument types in the 1990s.

The NiTi alloy has 3 distinct, temperature dependent, microstructural phases: Austenite, Martensite, and R-phase.¹²

Austenite is a high temperature phase. This phase exhibits superelastic mechanical characteristics and demonstrates minimal plastic deformation.¹³ In this phase, the metal exhibits

increased rigidity. The conventional NiTi alloy predominantly exists in the austenite phase at room temperature. Instruments made from austenitic materials exhibit restricted flexibility and exhibit a low tolerance to fatigue.¹²

Manufacturers employ a particular thermomechanical process to create soft and ductile instruments that can be easily deformed, leading to the production of a NiTi alloy predominantly featuring a stable martensite phase. These modifications enhance the physical properties of the rotating NiTi files, resulting in increased efficiency in dentin cutting and improved fracture resistance.¹²

R-phase is produced through a 2 stage grinding process followed by twisting. It serves as an intermediate phase between austenite and martensite.

The innovative M-wire technology is employed to manufacture instruments that exhibit exceptional elasticity. This method involves subjecting the NiTi wire to multiple heat treatments throughout the manufacturing process. Dentsply Protaper Next rotary files are obtained through M-wire technology.¹⁴ Protaper Next represents an innovative collection of rotary instruments characterized by their variable tapers and an off-centered rectangular cross-section.¹⁵

New NiTi instruments, developed through specialized thermomechanical processes, can change to a martensite phase when used clinically, by being able to control the memory of the file. This characteristic, referred to as "Control Memory," enhances their flexibility and increases their resistance to fracture.¹⁶ Mani Jizai instruments feature a distinctive asymmetrical cross-sectional design, resulting in an offset mass of rotation.¹⁷

An additional development in the production process of NiTi alloy is the R-Phase technology.¹⁸ Sybron Endo Twisted Files are produced using this technology. The manufacturing process involves two rounds of grinding, which are subsequently followed by a twisting procedure.¹⁹

In the current investigation, the sterilized instruments exhibited a diminished cyclic fatigue resistance compared to their non-sterilized counterparts. This finding suggests that the autoclaving process leads to a notable decrease in cyclic fatigue resistance, likely due to the elevated temperature and pressure involved, which may alter the metallurgical properties and subsequently impact the integrity and flexibility of the file. Additionally, the autoclaving cycles enhanced the depth of surface irregularities on the file, which serve as sites for stress concentration and the initiation of cracks. This would make the instruments more susceptible to fatigue crack propagation, resulting in reduced cutting efficiency and diminished resistance to wear.¹

In the present study, Mani Jizai displayed a greater number of cycles to fracture among the sterilized and the non-sterilized files. When comparison was done between the Dentsply Protaper Next and the Twisted Files, it was seen that Protaper Next displayed a greater number of cycles to fracture among the sterilized and non-

sterilized files.

Within the limitations of this in-vitro study, autoclave sterilization of newer endodontic instruments decreases resistance to cyclic fatigue. Autoclave sterilization significantly decreases the resistance to cyclic fatigue of Mani Jizai, Dentsply Protaper Next, and Twisted files. Cyclic fatigue resistance was higher in Mani Jizai files, as compared to the other files.

Conclusion

Mani Jizai files has a significantly higher cyclic fatigue resistance compared with the Dentsply Protaper Next and Sybron Endo Twisted files. Dentsply Protaper Next is significantly more resistant to fatigue compared with Twisted Files. The cyclic fatigue resistance of non-sterilized files was significantly higher than that of sterilized files.

As this is an in-vitro study, the results cannot be extrapolated to the clinical scenario. In clinical contexts, cyclic as well as torsional stresses act on the files which are affected by numerous clinical factors which cannot be replicated in an in-vitro study. Also, instruments undergo sterilization procedures after use, whereas in the study, the files have been used before sterilization also.

A final aspect of our study that limits its clinical relevance is the fact that the tested files rotated in contact with stainless steel plate which is different from dentin.

As the effect of clinical use was not evaluated in this study, further clinical investigations should be performed to better understand the combined effects of canal instrumentation and autoclaving.

References

1. Al-Amidi AH, Al-Gharrawi HA. Effect of autoclave sterilization on the cyclic fatigue resistance of EdgeFile X7, 2Shape, and F-one nickel-titanium endodontic instruments. *J Conserv Dent.* 2023 Jan-Feb; 26 (1): 26-30
2. Martins JNR, Silva EJNL, Marques D, Braz Fernandes FM, Versiani MA. Comprehensive Assessment of Cyclic Fatigue Strength in Five Multiple File Nickel Titanium Endodontic Systems. *Materials.* 2024 May; 17 (10): 2345.
3. Sharroufna R, Mashyakhly M. The Effect of Multiple Autoclave Sterilization on the Cyclic Fatigue of Three Heat Treated Nickel Titanium Rotary Files: EdgeFile X7, Vortex Blue, and TRUShape. *Biomed Res Int.* 2020 Dec 14; 2020: 8826069.
4. Almohareb, R.A., Barakat, R.; Albakri, A.; Altamimi, M. Effect of Autoclaving Cycles on the Cyclic Fatigue Resistance of Race and Race Evo Nickel-Titanium Endodontic Rotary Files: An In Vitro Study. *Metals.* 2021 Dec; 11 (12): 1947.
5. Gayatri K, Tammineedi S, Bolla N, Vemuri S, Basam RC, Sunil CR. Effect of autoclaving on the cyclic fatigue resistance of nickel titanium rotary instruments: An in vitro study. *J Conserv Dent.* 2021 Sep-Oct; 24 (5): 440-444

6. Pedullà E, Benites A, La Rosa GM, Plotino G, Grande NM, Rapisarda E, Generali L. Cyclic Fatigue Resistance of Heat treated Nickel titanium Instruments after Immersion in Sodium Hypochlorite and/or Sterilization. *J Endod.* 2018 Apr; 44 (4): 648-653.
7. Hajer M, Elhamid A. Cyclic Fatigue Resistance of newly introduced Surface and Thermal treated Nickel Titanium Rotary files. *Egypt Dent J.* 2020 Jan; 66 (1): 683-694.
8. Pérez-Higueras JJ, Arias A, de la Macorra JC. Cyclic fatigue resistance of K3, K3XF, and twisted file nickel titanium files under continuous rotation or reciprocating motion. *J Endod.* 2013 Dec; 39 (12):1585-8.
9. Shen Y, Qian W, Abtin H, Gao Y, Haapasalo M. Fatigue testing of controlled memory wire nickel titanium rotary instruments. *J Endod.* 2011 July; 37 (7): 997-1001.
10. Chopra K, Ballal NV. Comparison of Surface Defects in Different Rotary Files: An in-vitro study. *PBOCI.* 2024 Dec; 25: 1-8.
11. Stosic N, Popovic J, Stankovic A, Mitic A, Nikolic M, Todorovic K. The influence of autoclave sterilization on the cyclic fatigue of M-wire rotary endodontic instruments. *SC Indeks.* 2024 Aug; 81 (10): 642-647
12. Stošić N, Popović J, Anđelković Apostolović M, Mitić A, Nikolić M, Barac R, Kostić M. Effects of Autoclave Sterilization on Cyclic Fatigue Resistance in 5 Types of Rotary Endodontic Instruments: An In Vitro Study. *Med Sci Monit.* 2023 Mar 27; 29: e939694
13. Grande NM, Castagnola R, Minciacci I, Marigo L, Plotino G. A review of the latest developments in rotary NiTi technology and root canal preparation. *Aust Dent J.* 2023 Jun; 68 Suppl 1: S24-S38.
14. Stosic N, Popovic J, Stankovic A, Mitic A, Nikolic M, Todorovic K. The influence of autoclave sterilization on the cyclic fatigue of M-wire rotary endodontic instruments. *SC Indeks.* 2024 Aug; 81 (10): 642-647
15. Pereira ES, Singh R, Arias A, Peters OA. In vitro assessment of torque and force generated by novel ProTaper Next Instruments during simulated canal preparation. *J Endod.* 2013 Dec; 39 (12):1615-9.
16. Zevallos-Quiroz CA, Perez IE, Garcia-Rupaya CR. Efficacy of Controlled Memory and Shape Memory Nickel Titanium Instruments in Removing Filling Material from Severely Curved Root Canals: An Ex Vivo Study. *Iran Endod J.* 2019 Spring; 14 (2): 115-121.
17. Bürklein S, Donnermeyer D, Hentschel TJ, Schäfer E. Shaping Ability and Debris Extrusion of New Rotary Nickel-Titanium Root Canal Instruments. *Materials (Basel).* 2021 Feb 24; 14 (5):1063.
18. Pujari H. Stress distribution of new generation of Twisted Files in comparison with ProTaper: A finite element analysis. *Saudi Endod J.* 2013 May-Aug; 3 (2): 65-69
19. K Asha, Ghivari S, Pujar M, Sait S. NiTi rotary system in endodontics – An overview. *IP Indian Journal of Conservative and Endodontics.* 2023; 8 (3):128-133.